

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROCESS OF SIZES ACCORDING TO THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE INTERNATIONAL STANDARD

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Abstract: *Magnitudes are many and varied, but all of them are explained by only two descriptions. These are qualitative and quantitative descriptions. Qualitative description is a description that expresses the nature and content of the received quantity. Often, the terms parameter, quality indicator, description (characteristic) can be used instead of the quantity, but it is clarified that all these terms essentially represent the quantity. Sizes are many and varied, but all of them are explained by only two descriptions. These are qualitative and quantitative descriptions. Qualitative description is a description that expresses the nature and content of the received quantity. Often, the terms parameter, quality indicator, description (characteristic) can be used instead of the quantity, but it is clarified that all these terms essentially represent the quantity.*

Key words: *magnitude, invariant, electrical, mechanical, parameter, quality, unit of mass, process, property, general, quantity, states, mass, time, weight, quality indicator, description.*

Names are given to the descriptions of objects and events in animate and inanimate nature that exist in life. The differences between these descriptions are defined by these names. So "what is that thing, what is this thing?" concepts with definitions that answer the questions appear. Throughout history, the number of concepts has continuously increased and continues to increase. In some cases, it is possible to use a physical quantity instead of a concept [1].

In this case, the relevant descriptions should be such that it should be possible to determine the unit and perform measurements for it. In it, the laws of nature are

formed in the form of mathematical expressions for these quantities. This allows you to make calculations according to the general rules of mathematics [2].

It can be said that quantities are considered to be measured if it is known how many times a unit is contained within that quantity. The numerical value of the quantity {G} is the number of times the unit is in the quantity. If we symbolically designate the unit of magnitude G as [G] (the unit of time is 1 second, the unit of current is 1 Ampere), then

$$[G] = \frac{G}{\{G\}} \quad (1)$$

A numerical value is considered a pure number, without any additional information. This expression, $G = \{G\}[G]$ (2) it will be possible to give it in appearance [3].

Therefore, indicating the value of the quantity G (showing its measured value) requires also indicating the corresponding unit. That is, if the electric current I in the conductor is 10 times greater than its unit 1 Ampere (1 A), then the current will be equal to $I = 10 \text{ A}$ (note that not 10 [A], but always $10 [I] = 10 \text{ A}$).

Numerical values of very large or very small (compared to 10) order, which lead to inconvenience, are reduced and expressed by adding additions using new discharges with the old name of the unit (so new units appear, for example, $1 \text{ mm}^3 = 1 \cdot (10^{-3} \text{ m})^3 = 10^{-9} \text{ m}^3$). The physical size itself does not change because

$$G = \{G\}[G] = \{FG\}[G/F] = \{G'\}[G']. \quad (3)$$

If we decrease the unit by F times, then the numerical value also increases by F times. Such invariance of a physical quantity is preserved not only when the unit is changed to some number by ten degrees, but also when this unit is changed in other ways, for example, when changing the meter to inches [4].

Before giving the definition of magnitudes, let's give an introduction to their essence. You will see all kinds of things, animate and inanimate objects. Although these listed are quite different from each other, we can see some

commonalities in the features and characteristics that we need to look at now. For example, take a pen, a desk, and your friend. No matter how different they are from each other, they have such a commonality that all three of them are described in the same way. If we are talking about their bigness and smallness, then we understand the space or distance that is taken in a certain direction and has a clear border [5].

This property has the same meaning for all three objects. From the point of view of this meaning, the difference between them remains only in value. Or if we take the concept of weight, i.e., the characteristic of objects taken as an example, which represents the attraction to the Earth, we see the same content. In this case, the difference between them is only in the large or small force of their attraction to the Earth, that is, in their value. We simply call it weight. There are only a few such properties, and they are given the name of magnitude [6].

Sizes are many and varied, but all of them are explained by only two descriptions. These are qualitative and quantitative descriptions.

Qualitative description is a description that expresses the nature and content of the received quantity. When it comes to distance, we understand the property that indicates the size, length, or height of a certain object, that is, we bring it to our eyes. We can know this from a simple experience. Put aside your other work for a minute and bring before your eyes the quantities called weight and temperature... Well, have you noticed their qualitative characteristics? Pay attention to something, when you say weight, you have in mind some abstract, heavy or light object, most often scales, when it comes to temperature and you embodied something that signifies hotness and coldness. These are the qualitative descriptions of the magnitude that we are trying to explain to you [7].

Now, if we talk about a certain size in the obtained objects, we will see that these objects more or less "embody" this size. This is a quantitative description of magnitude. Now we can give the definition of size: Magnitude

is a property that is qualitatively general to many physical objects (physical systems, their states and processes occurring in them), and quantitatively specific to each object. The specificity given in the definition means that the property of an object is greater or smaller in comparison to another [8].

The science of metrology that we are studying is closely related to these quantities, their units, and the development of measurement techniques. It is not correct to use the term "magnitude" to express only the quantitative aspect of a property (for example, to write "magnitude of mass", "magnitude of pressure"), because these properties themselves are magnitudes. In this case, it is correct to use the term "size". For example, the length, mass, electrical resistance, etc. of a known object. Each physical object can be characterized by a number of objective properties. With the progress and development of science, the demand to know these properties is increasing. By now, it is possible to measure more than 70 sizes using modern measuring tools. It is predicted that this figure will exceed 200 by 2050 [9].

Often, instead of size, we come across the terms parameter, quality indicator, description (characteristic), but all these terms essentially represent size. There is a correlation between quantities in certain groups, which can be expressed through physical coupling equations. For example, we can determine the speed by the distance traveled per unit of time. Based on these connections, quantities are divided into two groups: basic quantities and derived quantities. The main quantity is a quantity that enters into the system and is considered independent of other quantities of the system. For example, distance (length), time, temperature, light intensity [10].

A derived quantity is a quantity that enters the system and is expressed by the system quantities. For example, speed, acceleration, electrical resistance, power, etc. Since each property can be expressed to a greater or lesser degree, that is, have a quantitative description, it means that this property can also be measured. The great Italian scientist Galileo Galilei said about this: "Measure what can be measured, and create a possibility for what

is impossible." We use dimensionality to express qualitative descriptions of quantities in a formal way. The size of a quantity is an expression that shows the relationship of this quantity with the main quantities in the system and the proportionality coefficient is equal to 1. Dimension is defined by the dim symbol, based on the (visual) word meaning dimension [11].

Typically, the size of key quantities is indicated by appropriate capital letters, e.g.

$$\dim l = L; \dim m = M; \dim t = T.$$

When determining the size of derivative quantities, the following rules should be followed: 1. The size of the right and left sides of the equation may not match. because only identical properties can be compared. If we conclude from this, we can add algebraically only quantities that have the same size.

2. The algebra of dimensions is multiplicative, that is, it consists only of multiplication:

2.1. The size of the product of several quantities is equal to the product of their sizes, that is: if the relationship between the values of the quantities A, B, C, Q

is given in the form $Q = ABC$, then

$$\dim Q = (\dim A)(\dim B)(\dim C).$$

2.2. The size of the division when dividing one quantity by another is equal to the ratio of their sizes, that is, if $Q = A/B$, then

$$\dim Q = \dim A / \dim B .$$

2.3. The size of an arbitrary quantity raised to a power is equal to its size raised to this power, that is, if $Q = A^n$, then

$$\dim Q = \dim A^n.$$

For example, if the speed $v = l/t$, then

$$\dim v = \dim l / \dim t = L/T = LT^{-1}.$$

Thus, we can use the following formula to express the size of the derivative quantity:

$$\dim Q = L^n M^m T^k ,$$

where, L, M, T..., - the size of the main quantities, respectively; n, m, k..., - the degree of dimension [12].

The exponent of each dimension can be positive or negative, integer or fractional, or zero. If all exponents are equal to zero, then such a quantity is called a dimensionless quantity. This quantity can be relative (for example, dielectric conductivity), logarithmic (for example, the logarithmic ratio of electric power and voltage), determined by the ratio of quantities of the same name.

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